

GAMES BASED LEARNING IN TEACHING OF MATHEMATICS AT LOWER SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. The paper is about Games Based Learning in teaching of mathematics at lower secondary school. Our experience from using of didactical games and results from our previous researches on efficacy of teaching of mathematics with the method of didactical games are basis for our discussion about integration of games in the mathematics at lower secondary school and influences of these games on pupils' mathematical knowledge, their attitudes towards mathematics and process of its teaching and development of their key competencies. The output of this discussion is positive statement about increase of mathematics education quality by the integration of proper didactical games into mathematics lessons. The goal of our paper is then to present possibilities of Games Based Learning in teaching of mathematics at lower secondary school and to inspire teachers for including of proper didactical games into mathematics education.

Résumé. Notre article traite l'utilisation des jeux didactiques dans l'enseignement des mathématiques au deuxième cycle (collège). Le but de notre article est de présenter le potentiel des jeux didactiques dans l'enseignement des mathématiques au deuxième cycle et de motiver le cadre des enseignants de s'inspirer de ces jeux. Nos expériences et les résultats de nos recherches précédentes concernant l'efficacité de cette méthode forment la base de notre discussion: l'intégration des jeux dans les classes et leur déroulement; l'influence de ces jeux sur les connaissances et sur l'attitude des élèves par rapport aux mathématiques; le développement des compétences – clés. L'affirmation que la qualité de l'éducation mathématique accroît si on y intègre des jeux didactiques conclut notre discussion.

Zusammenfassung. Der Artikel behandelt die Verwendung von didaktischen Spielen in der Mathematikunterricht auf Hauptschulen. Unsere Erfahrungen mit der Anwendung didaktischer Spiele und die Ergebnisse unseren vorigen Forschungen einschlägig der Effektivität der Mathematikunterricht mit die Methode der didaktischen Spielen sind die Grundlage für eine weitere Diskussion bezüglich der Integration der Spiele ins Mathematikunterricht auf Hauptschulen und bezüglich der Einfluss dieser Spiele an die Mathematikkenntnisse der Schüler, ihrer Einstellung zum Mathematik und zum Lauf ihrer Unterricht und die Entwicklung von Schlüsselkompetenzen. Die Schlussfolgerung dieser Diskussion ist eine These über die Steigerung der Qualität der Mathematischer Ausbildung durch der Integration von entsprechenden didaktischen Spielen an Stunden der Mathematik. Das Ziel des Artikels ist es dieses Potential der didaktischen Spielen angewendeten in der Mathematikunterricht auf Hauptschulen zu präsentieren und ein breites Publikum der Schullehrer zum das Einreihung solchen Spiele in der Mathematikunterricht zu inspirieren.

Abstrakt. Článok pojednáva o integrácii didaktických hier do vyučovania matematiky na druhom stupni ZŠ. Naše skúsenosti s používaním týchto hier a výsledky našich predchádzajúcich výskumov týkajúcich sa efektívnosti vyučovania matematiky metódou didaktických hier sú podkladom pre ďalšiu diskusiu ohľadne vplyvu týchto hier na žiacke vedomosti, postoje k matematike a priebehu jej vyučovania a na rozvoj kľúčových kompetencií. Záverom tejto diskusie je tvrdenie o zvýšení kvality matematickej edukácie prostredníctvom integrácie vhodných didaktických hier na hodinách matematiky. Cieľom článku je teda prezentovať potenciál didaktických hier používaných vo vyučovaní matematiky na druhom stupni ZŠ a inšpirovať širokú učiteľskú verejnosť pre zaradenia takýchto hier do vyučovania matematiky.

Key words: didactical game, mathematics, knowledge, attitudes, efficacy, experimental research

1 INTRODUCTION

In modern educational theories is highlighted necessity of pupils' activity during lessons. There is also demand for development of not only pupils' knowledge but all key competencies. So we need teaching methods able to fulfil these needs. Very promising seems to be the method of teaching by didactical games.

As didactical game we consider activity of pupils which realize some educational goals and bring to pupils happiness and pleasure. This is very nice and comprehensive definition of didactical game (Průcha, Walterová and Mareš, 1998, p. 48, translated by author):

Didactical game: Analogy of spontaneous children's activity, which realize (for children not every time evidently) educational goals. Can take place in classroom, sport-hall, playground, or in the nature. Each game has its rules, needs continuous management and final assessment. It is suitable for single child either for group of children. Teacher has various roles: from main coordinator to an onlooker. Its advantage is motivational factor: it raises interest, makes higher children's involvement in teaching activities, and encourages children's creativity, spontaneity, co-operation and also competitiveness. Children can use their knowledge, abilities and experience. Some didactical games approach to model situations from real life.

There are researches on efficacy of the using of didactical games in mathematics education (see chapter Didactical Games). According to their results the games seem to be asset in the area of pupils attitudes towards mathematics and process of its teaching and some games are also useful tool for

better construction of mathematical knowledge. Therefore there is need to find new games for realization of various educational goals and inquire their efficacy and influences on teaching process.

In this article we present results of our researches on influences of some didactical games on pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching and on their mathematical knowledge. Then we discuss on the basis of these results question if games based learning (GBL) increase quality of mathematics education at lower secondary school. In the appendix 1 we also introduce for better illustration of discussed topic one didactical game that we used in our researches and our observation from its using at mathematics lessons and also pupils' reactions.

2 DIDACTICAL GAMES

Using of didactical games in pupils education has long tradition throughout the history (see Vankúš, 2005a). So it came also in focus of researches in the theory of mathematics education.

Randel, Morris, Wetzel and Whitehill (1992) referred that using of didactical games during mathematics' teaching can support pupils' motivation and performance during lessons. The active children's participation during the games is the need for better understanding and memorizing of taught mathematical knowledge.

Pulos and Sneider (1994) found out that properly chosen didactical game helps children to learn new mathematical notions and skills. These researchers recommended putting games into mathematics' curriculum as an auxiliary activity. They found out that experience gained trough proper didactical game used after mathematics lessons, dealing with the same mathematical notions and skills as the lessons, leaded to better understanding and more durable memorizing of taught knowledge.

E. Krejčová and M. Volfová in their work (1994) highlighted big value of game as a vital part of education. Putting didactical game into education enlarge, in accordance with authors, pupils interest in active work during mathematics' lessons and overall interest in mathematics. It improves whole process of mathematics lessons. As a positive feature of didactical game they referred about necessary integration of knowledge from different parts of mathematics curriculum and also from different subjects.

Positive influences of games on development of primary school children described in her work J. Cejpeková (1996). She has seen potential of didactical game in these areas:

Didactical game:

- *makes pupils active,*

- *develops their memory, imagination, concentration, thinking and speech,*
- *refines pupils' feelings area, supports learning by experience,*
- *improves self-confidence and self-cognition,*
- *makes possible social learning, prepares for various social situations,*
- *motivates, develops interests, satisfies needs, leads to creativity and self-reliance,*
- *has important influence as relax.*

M. Zelinová made precise analysis of functions of game in children's development. According to author game has important role in development of these areas of personality (1999):

Noncognitive areas:

- *feelings and positive experience, improvement of self-confidence,*
- *bigger activity and motivation,*
- *social behaviour, better social skills,*
- *boost of creativity, pleasure of creative activities.*

Cognitive areas:

- *sensory and motoric functions,*
- *memory,*
- *abilities to evaluate,*
- *creative thinking.*

G. Booker, Australian pedagogue, has used games in education at primary schools. He described the experience and observation from using of didactical games in his work *The Maths Games* (2000). Let us mention some of them:

Game is for children funny activity that brings motivation and full interest of pupils what is essential for constructive teaching. Children that are not willing learn to pleasure their parents or teacher or because the reason that mathematics will be necessary for their future life often learn by their own will in the frame of the social interaction with other pupils. Game gives context real for children...

From these reasons game have important place in mathematics education. It offers conditions in which is possible to construct and develop mathematical concepts. Game improves pupils' ability to solve problems by the need to explore and to use new strategies and refines other skills by the means of using these skills in the frame of game. It supports social interactions those lead to learning.

Author of this article has performed research on didactical games in mathematics education already in his diploma thesis (Vankúš, 2002). It was dealing with strategical mathematical games (didactical games, where we can think about winning strategy or at least about tactic) and their use in mathematics teaching. Experiment was realized in mathematics club for children 11–14 years old. We tested 6 strategical mathematical games and tried to find out their winning strategy or at least if such a strategy could exist. At the end of experiment we questioned pupils by questionnaire about their attitudes towards games we had used during experiment and about their opinions of using the strategical games during school mathematics lessons. From 17 pupils which took part in the experiment 11 stated that they were interested in all used games, 6 of them were interested in some of these games, and 0 were not interested in any of used games. 15 pupils were keen on idea to integrate strategical mathematical games in their mathematics lessons. So, pupils' statements about used games were positive, they like also the idea to use similar games during mathematics education.

In already mentioned work (Vankúš, 2005a) we studied history of using the games in education, especially in mathematics teaching and also present researches dealing with this subject. We also analysed how didactical games can help in overcoming main learning obstacles (Brousseau, 1986; Spagnolo and Margolinas, 1993). We find out that history of didactical games in mathematics education showed increase in using of these games as effective teaching method. Positive are also results of researches on efficacy of mathematics teaching by the help of proper didactical games. On the basis of our experience with didactical games we also concluded that these games are really useful for overcoming some of didactical obstacles.

In the article published in *Quaderni Di Ricerca In Didattica* (Vankúš, 2005b) we also discussed structure of didactical games according Brousseau's Theory of didactical situations (Brousseau, 1997). We analyzed these four main parts of didactical game:

- Milieu of the game
- Goals of game
- Activities of teacher and pupils, which are determine with rules of game
- Final evaluation

Interactions between pupils and milieu of didactical game should motivate pupils to the work. This work leads to the realisation of goals of game. The goals of game are dedicated to educational goals, which have to be realised by the game. The goals of game determine form of game. Usage of didactical games has value only if it enables to reach educational goals.

Activities of teacher and pupils, which are determined with rules of game, should be for pupils attractive and motivational. These activities have to be suitable for age of pupils and their abilities. The rules of game determine the form and organisation of pupils' work. The rules include gamesome elements (e.g. competitiveness between teams of pupils).

Final evaluation verifies realisation of game's goals and have to reward pupils and motivate them for the next activities.

Very important for the using of didactical games in mathematics education is for teachers the methodology how to work with this teaching method. In our article (Vankúš 2006) we identified three important phases of this methodology:

1. Selection of proper game suitable for the use at mathematics lesson. The game should be able to fulfil educational goals of the lesson. Moreover, the game should be proper for the age, knowledge level and interests of the pupils. Also practical realization of the game should be easy in the terms of teacher's preparation for the lesson, necessary material tools needed for realization of the game and also the process of the game.

2. Realization of the game at the mathematics lesson. The presentation of the game we begin with its name. This name should be attractive for pupils and also should characterize content of the game. Then we present rules of the game – the best is to illustrate rules on some examples of the game process. Next come playing the game by the pupils. It can have form of a team competition. Teacher controls process of the game and keeping of the game rules during this activity.

3. Assessment of the pupils' work during the game. As every human activity also pupils' activity during didactical game should be assessed. Because the character of the game we use only positive assessment, for example winner acquires some number of positive points, the second player acquires also some positive points, but less than the winner. This way of the assessing of the didactical games motivates pupils for really great effort during game process.

We also published electronic collection of didactical games suitable for the use at lower secondary school mathematics in order to help teachers to work with didactical games (<http://www.ddm.fmph.uniba.sk/ZH/>, in Slovak). This collection is designed for mathematics teachers willing to use didactical games. It comprises short definition of didactical game, chapter dealing with methodology how to use didactical games during mathematics lessons and 27 didactical games, which are suitable for integration to certain themes of mathematics education at lower secondary school. At the end of collection is table, where are the games grouped according to mathematics themes they are designed for. The themes are ordered in accordance with the mathematics curriculum used at the most of lower secondary schools in Slovakia.

3 RESULTS OF RECENT RESEARCH

In this chapter we present results of our recent research dealing with influences of some chosen didactical games on pupils' mathematical knowledge and attitudes towards mathematics and process of its teaching. This research we performed during work on our doctoral thesis (Vankúš, 2006b). Some of results concerning attitudes were presented at the CERME 5 conference (2007, Cyprus, Larnaca).

The research had experimental character and was conducted in two phases. In both phases experimental samples were two classes of the fifth grade (pupils 11–12 years old), one of them was experimental, the second one control class. Together 103 pupils took part in our experiment, in the first phase experimental class had 25 pupils, control class had 26 pupils and in the second phase both classes had 26 pupils. In the experimental classes we taught with integration of didactical games into mathematics education, in control classes without them. Experiment took 17 mathematics lessons, taught theme was geometry, in concrete area of plane objects. Used were 5 didactical games, two of them took whole lesson; three were used at the end of lesson and took 10–20 minutes.

Research questions were:

Q1 Would used didactical games positively influence pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching?

Q2 How would didactical games affect pupils' knowledge from mathematical theme taught during experiment?

To find out answers to our research questions we used these methods:

M1 Questionnaire constructed to measure pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and process of its teaching (appendix 2). This questionnaire is based on questionnaire used by R. F. Mager (Mager, 1984) and concept of attitudes as defined in Ruffell et al., 1998. More about used concept of attitudes see in Schlöglmann, 2003; Zan and Martino, 2003. The questionnaire was used twice, at the beginning of experimental teaching and at the end. Results of questionnaires were compared, thus we could say how the using of didactical games influenced studied indicators.

M2 Test to measure knowledge from taught theme (appendix 3). Test was created by standard procedure (see Turek, 1996). It contains 14 tasks dealing with knowledge and computing skill from taught theme. Results of test were compared to results of control class where pupils were taught the same theme but without didactical games. (Classes were similar in number of pupils, in both classes taught the same teacher.)

M3 To observe pupils' reactions on didactical games we studied pupils' behaviour during whole experiment and performed some interviews.

By the method M1 we found out that there was increase in questionnaires' score in experimental classes (see fig. 1)

Fig. 1 Average score of questionnaires

The increase is significant especially when we consider that in the control classes we observed decrease in questionnaires' score. This decrease was likely due to difficulty of taught theme for pupils. In the control classes pupils regarded this theme as not so interesting. But in the experimental classes where we used didactical games students after experiment had according to results of questionnaire better attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching. By the means of statistical analysis we analysed differences in the initial values and final values of the average scores in the items of questionnaire (by the use of paired 2 tailed Student t-test) and we found out that these differences are statistically significant (in the first phase $\alpha = 0.05$, in the second phase $\alpha = 0.005$)

The knowledge from theme taught during experiment we compared on the basis of test results (see fig. 2 and fig. 3).

Fig. 2 Average proportional score in the tasks of the test in the first phase of the experiment

Fig. 3 Average proportional score in the tasks of the test in the second phase of the experiment

Although average proportional score in the tasks varied used statistical test (Student's 2 tailed unpaired t-test) showed that the differences in the results of test in the experimental and the control class were in both phases statistically

insignificant. Using of our didactical games did not change pupils' knowledge in comparison with mathematics teaching without these didactical games.

On the basis of our observation we can say that didactical games are for children impetus for their active participation during games activities. Pupils were motivated by competitiveness to win game alone in the case of pair games or to help their team gain the best score in the case of team games. Playing of some games is for children motivational also because of interesting game environment. Pupils often play interesting game also at home, they teach it their friends and for example in the case of strategical games they are thinking about the winning strategy also during their free time. This motivation is evident likewise during games where pupils have to solve some mathematical tasks. Pupils are doing their best to solve as many tasks as is possible often greatly overcoming number of tasks solved during work without games environment. By the help of didactical games is mathematics and doing of mathematical computation for children more interesting and important because it is mean to be a winner or to experience something funny during playing of the games. We have also noticed that during playing of team games pupils very actively communicate their mathematical knowledge and skills needed to play the game. In the case of team games are also important social skills for organizing of team work. So didactical games are support also in developing of pupils communication and social skills. Playing of strategical mathematical games is also opportunity for developing of pupils' argumentation and logical skills during analyzing of game strategy and searching for the winning strategy.

So in this recent research we found out that used didactical games are suitable for improvement of pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching. Result of questionnaire showed that used didactical games improved pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching.

Results of didactical test from mathematics themes taught during our experiment showed that pupils' knowledge in experimental classes were statistically the same as knowledge in classes where we did not use the games. This knowledge was achieved in both classes during the same time amount so integration of didactical games did not hinder the pace of teaching process.

Our observations showed that pupils liked the work with the games and they were motivated for active participation during mathematics lessons where these games were integrated. We noticed that some didactical games are good opportunity for developing of pupils' communication skills, argumentation skills, social skills and logical skills. Some of these skills are important key competencies (Gibb, 2004).

4 CONCLUSION

Our paper discussed GBL in teaching of mathematics at lower secondary school. After brief introduction where we discussed the notion didactical game we present some researches dealing with using of didactical games in mathematics teaching. These researches inquired influences of the games on pupils' knowledge and skills, their motivation, performance and also influences on pupils' personal development. Some researches studied also practical methodology how to use the games in educational process.

In the next part of our article we present results of our recent research on didactical games. The research was experimental and it was inquiring influences of five didactical games on pupils' mathematical knowledge and their attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching. In the research we compared these variables in control and experimental sample. We registered improvement of pupils' attitudes; knowledge was statistically equal in both groups.

On the basis of previous researches dealing with using of didactical games in mathematics education and also on the basis of our own researches we can identify potential of didactical games for mathematics teaching. This potential is considering results of our recent research also in improving of pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching. We can say that this is important considering significant role of attitudes for motivation of learning activities and therefore integration of proper didactical games can increase quality of mathematics education.

Crucial for the integration of didactical games in mathematics education is to performed further researches on efficacy of chosen games and then make collection of games proven to be worth using in educational process. In the future we plan to test more didactical games and create collection of such effective games corresponding with mathematics curriculum at lower secondary school. Afterwards we will realize research on influences of teaching by the help of created collection. Obtained results could answer statistically more significantly important questions about GBL in mathematics.

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Appendix 1

In this appendix we describe one didactical game used in our researches. The name of game is Snake and it is dealing with point symmetry. We present educational goals of this game, its rules, realization in mathematics class, assessment of pupils' work and our observation on pupils' reactions and on the game itself.

SNAKE

Educational goals:

Snake is didactical game proper for the use during teaching of the point symmetry. The aim of this game can be to practice the point symmetry transformation or even to teach pupils basic knowledge and notions linked with this symmetry. The game also develops pupils' strategical thinking.

Rules:

This game is played by whole class divided to pairs of pupils. At the beginning each pair gets game board that has 36 squares (6 rows and 6 columns). The player A draws in one square the circle and writes to it number 1. It means that snake has been born and actually has one day. The player B then select one point where is crossed vertical and horizontal line of the square grid and transform the snake in the point symmetry to its new place (figure 4a). Then the player B adds one new circle to the square that is one place in the vertical or horizontal direction from the place of the snake (figure 4b). To these two circles are written numbers 2 – snake moved and it has 2 days. In the next move player A again select one point where is crossed vertical and horizontal line of the square grid (can be also point already used) and in the point symmetry moves the snake and also adds one new circle – snake again moved and is 3 days old (figure 4c). The players shift their moves till one player can not find how to move the snake to the free squares or can not add one new circle. This player loses the game, the second player wins. The example of one game shows figure 5.

Figure 4a

Figure 4b

Figure 4c

The moves in game Snake

Figure 5 Example of game Snake

Realization:

As was already said this game can be used for practicing of point symmetry and also as propaedeutics of this mathematics theme. In the first case is game played by stable pair of pupils or there is the possibility to organize team competition. We divide class into even number of teams. Each team plays against another team. That means one player of the team plays for example 2 games against one randomly chosen player from opposite team. The winning brings 2 points for the team, the draw 1 point for each team and the loose 0 points. Each team plays each other and the team with the biggest points gain is the winner of the competition. From our experience we can say that such competition is impetus for really great pupils' interest. Pupils play numbers of games. They enjoy it forgetting that they are in fact doing mathematics. Very often they play the game also at home and teach its rules their friends. Teacher's role during such competition is to control keeping of rules and at the beginning of game to explain problems with game rules. There is usually no need to keep discipline and stir pupils into activity; they are motivated by the game. So the game is very good practice of point symmetry, pupils are doing a lot of point symmetry transformation of different shapes as the snake is growing and they are developing also their strategic thinking. All this is done in very enjoyable way.

When we use this game as propaedeutics of point symmetry there is difference in explaining of game rules. We can not say that move of the snake is transformation of its previous position in the point symmetry because pupils do not know this notion. Instead we can use explanation in the figure 6 and following text.

Figure 6 Explaining of the rules for children without knowledge about point symmetry

We have initial position of the circle. Then is selected a point. Initial position of the snake is three columns on the left from the point and two rows above the point. So the next position of the circle will be three columns on the right and two rows under the selected point. Children understand this explanation well; we can solve some task where they should find new position of the snake for the practice before the game (figure 7).

Figure 7 Examples of tasks

Before the starting of the game playing we can also inquire answer on questions like what is the distance between the initial and final position of circle and the selected point or what you receive when you make line linking initial and final position of the circle. Answers on these questions are uncovering some important features of point symmetry. So this game used as the propaedeutics of point symmetry can be really good introduction into this mathematics theme.

Assessment:

In the case that game is not played in the team competition each player has own assessment. The pupils play more games (at least two with one opponent to insure that each player makes first move in the game the same number of times). For each game winner gets 3 points and second player 1 point. At the end of game are points summed and the score can be transformed to positive points into mathematics assessment of pupils.

The assessment in the case that game is played in the team competition has been mentioned in the realization of the game.

Observation:

As was already said we have noticed very great potential of this game for practicing and propaedeutics of the point symmetry. Pupils enjoy this game and are doing really well during its playing. As additional positive things the game develops pupils' strategical thinking by planning of the moves.

Appendix 2

In this appendix we present questionnaire constructed to measure pupils' attitudes towards mathematics and process of its teaching. By this questionnaire we inquired influences of didactical games used in our research. After each item is attached score for the answers, this was not a part of questionnaire given to students.

QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear pupils, in these questions you have possibility to express your attitudes towards mathematics and its teaching. Questionnaire is anonymous, you don't subscribe yourselves. Your answers will be used as a part of research. Please, express openly your opinions.

Thank you very much for filling in the questionnaire.

1) Imagine that you are teacher. Which of following subjects would you like to teach the most?

- a) Languages
- b) Geography
- c) Mathematics
- d) Physics
- e) Natural science
- f) Other (write which):

Score: For marked answer c) 2 points, other answers for 0 points.

2) Subject mathematics is for you

- a) Very interesting
- b) Interesting
- c) Sometimes interesting, sometimes not interesting

- d) Uninteresting
e) Very uninteresting

Score: For answer a) 2 points, b) 1 point, c) 0 points, d) -1 point, e) -2 points.

- 3) Encircle every word from following that describes your attitudes towards mathematics.

- | | | | |
|----------------|-----------------|--------------|----------------|
| a) Interesting | b) Boring | c) Worthless | d) Monotonous |
| e) Useful | f) Entertaining | g) Easy | h) Important |
| i) Useless | j) Valuable | k) Difficult | l) Unimportant |

Score: For answers a), e), f), g), h), j) 1 point; for answers b), c), d), i), k), l) -1 point.

- 4) Can you remember some activities linked with mathematics that you like?

a) Yes

(Write them).....

b) No

Score: For each liked activity 1 point.

- 5) Which mark from mathematics did you have on your last school report?

a) 1 b) 2 c) 3 d) 4 e) 5

- 6) You look forward to having mathematics lesson:

a) Always b) Often c) Sometimes d) Rarely e) Never

Score: For answer a) 2 points, b) 1 point, c) 0 points, d) -1 point, e) -2 points.

Appendix 3

This appendix contains test by which we measured pupils' knowledge taught during our research, in concrete during teaching of mathematics theme dealing with area of plane objects. The score is written after each task. This was not part of original test.

KNOWLEDGE TEST

- 1) At what activities in life do we measure area? Write at least one of them:

.....

Score: 1 point for mentioning at least one activity.

- 2) State area of plane object in the square grid (one square of grid has area 1 cm^2).

Area of plane object is:

Score: 1 point for the right answer.

3) What units of area do you know? Write at least six different units:

.....
 Score: 1 point for writing at least six units of area.

4) Change:

- a) $720 \text{ dm}^2 = \dots\dots\dots \text{ m}^2$
- b) $12 \text{ cm}^2 = \dots\dots\dots \text{ mm}^2$
- c) $1,5 \text{ m}^2 = \dots\dots\dots \text{ cm}^2$
- d) $1200 \text{ mm}^2 = \dots\dots\dots \text{ dm}^2$
- e) $1,4 \text{ ha} = \dots\dots\dots \text{ a}$
- f) $10 \text{ a} = \dots\dots\dots \text{ m}^2$

Score: 0.5 points for each correct answer, maximum 3 points.

5) Write formula for area of rectangle and describe what means each letter in formula. Depict in the picture.

Score: 0.5 points for correct formula and 0.5 point for the right picture, maximum 1 point.

6) Calculate area of rectangle if its measures are $2,5 \text{ dm}$ and 10 cm .

Score: 1 point for correct answer.

7) Area of rectangle is 32 cm^2 and length of one rectangle's side is 8 cm . State the length of adjacent side of the rectangle.

Score: 1 point for correct answer.

8) Write formula for area of square and describe what means each letter in formula. Depict in the picture.

Score: 0.5 points for correct formula and 0.5 point for the right picture, maximum 1 point.

9) Calculate area of square if it has one side 5 dm long.

Score: 1 point for correct answer.

10) Area of square is 36 cm^2 . State the length of its side.

Score: 1 point for correct answer.

11) Area of square is 49 mm^2 . State its perimeter.

Score: 1 point for correct answer.

12) We want to pave the room depicted in the picture. State what amount of floor titles in m^2 we will need. Measures of the room in the picture are in metres.

Answer:

Score: 1 point for correct answer.

13) A fence around a square playground is 40 metres long. State the area of the playground. (Write process of your solving.)

Score: 1 point for correct notation of the task situation, 1 point for correct calculations and 1 point for the right answer, maximum 3 points.

14) We want to paint with brush walls of a rectangular room with measures 4 m and 2,5 m. How many tins of painting colour do we have to buy? We know that one tin is enough for painting 5 m² of the wall. (Write process of your solving.)

Score: 1 point for correct notation of the task situation, 1 point for correct calculations and 1 point for the right answer, maximum 3 points.